

Bio-sorption analysis of Cd^{II} from aqueous medium by activated *Citrus limetta* peel powder

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Abstract : The efficiency of the sweet lime (*Citrus limetta*) peel for the purpose of removal of cadmium(II) by using the technique of batch experiments has been analyzed. This species is mostly found in South and Southeast Asia and cultivated in Mediterranean Basin. Various parameters like pH, particle size, contact time, surface coverage values, mass of adsorbent, metal ion concentration, adsorption of Cd^{II} and their effect on the property of adsorption have been studied with the help of Freundlich and Langmuir adsorption isotherm model. The efficiency of sweet lime is compared with lemon (*Citrus lemon*).

Keywords : Bio-sorption, activated sweet lime peel powder, activated lemon peel powder, cadmium(II), adsorption isotherm, effluent treatment.

Introduction

Water containing industrial wastes is a major source of environmental pollution in recent days. The discharge of Industrial wastes, contain gigantic amount of heavy metals and phenolics. It needs to be mentioned here that these hazardous wastes if get concentrated in soil may harm not only plants but animals and humans too. Thus, it becomes indispensable to remove potentially toxic components of the sludge disposed from mining industries, chemical industries, metal processing industries and others¹.

The report of World Health Organization (WHO) has shown that the heavy metal cadmium is toxic for humans and beyond a certain range it proves fatal. In electroplating industries and paint industries workers are exposed to this hazardous metal. Over exposure to cadmium may cause "cadmium blues", chilling fever, dizziness, weakness, chest pain as common symptoms but severe condition may cause respiratory and kidney damage^{2,3}. It has been observed that there are many natural sites in the world that are contaminated by heavy metals. The efforts that already introduced in this field are probably less favorable in terms of economy and public acceptance. Natural renewable resources that have potential to be used as scientific tool are utilized in this research.

Methods like ion-exchange⁴, coagulation⁵, membrane filtration⁶, evaporation⁷ are expensive and do not always provide promising results. In recent years many work have been done for the same objective by using tamarind seeds, *Ziziphus jujube* leaf powder, bagasse, straw, tea factory waste, pine needles, soya cake, sugar industry waste⁸⁻¹⁵ etc. *Citrus limetta* is a species of Citrus which is known as sweet lemon or sweet lime. In South and North India it is known as mousambi. It grows in tropical as well as sub-tropical climate. It tastes much like lime but is essentially sweet and mild. It is often used in treatment of influenza and common cold.

Likewise, sweet lime that is abundantly available and is eco-friendly can be used as low cost adsorbent. The purpose of this study is to develop an effective method to use low cost sweet lime peel powder and compare its efficiency with lemon peel powder for removal of toxic cadmium(II) from industrial effluent.

Results and discussion

Effect of adsorbent dosage on removal efficiency :

The experiments were carried out, with change in biomass dosage of activated *Citrus limetta* peel powder from 3–15 g L⁻¹ while other variables were kept constant like particle size of biomass : 150 µm; metal ion concentra-

tion : 200 mg L⁻¹. The contact time was also maintained for 80 min at pH 4. The experiments were also carried out with *Citrus lemon* and the condition was same as taken for *Citrus limetta*.

The effect of biomass dosage on the removal of cadmium(II) ion is shown in Fig. 3. With the increase in biomass of adsorbent, the removal efficiency also increases. It is due to the fact that number of adsorption sites increases by increasing the adsorbent doses. We compared data of both the adsorbents and found that the removal efficiencies of *Citrus limetta* and *Citrus lemon* were found to be 61.5% and 31.1% respectively.

Effect of pH on removal efficiency :

The experiments were carried out, with the change in pH from 2–6 and maintaining others as constant i.e. adsorbent dosage 12 g L⁻¹; particle size of biomass 150 μm; the concentration of metal ion cadmium(II) 200 mg L⁻¹ at 80 min. As shown in Fig. 4, the metal ion removal efficiency of *Citrus limetta* and *Citrus lemon* increases up to pH 4 and then decreases because the electrostatic attraction between metal and hydrogen ion sites are reduced and thus the removal would be reduced. Maximum removal efficiency of *Citrus limetta* and *Citrus lemon* at pH 4 were 61.5% and 27.1% respectively.

Effect of particle size on removal efficiency :

The experiments were carried out, with change in particle size of biomass dosage of activated *Citrus limetta* and *Citrus lemon* peel powder from 100–300 μm, and along with maintaining other conditions constant i.e. adsorbent dosage 12 g L⁻¹; metal ion concentration 200 mg L⁻¹, 80 min contact time at pH 4. Fig. 5, shows that with the increase in particle size, the removal efficiency or percentage absorbance decreases. If particle size is large then surface area is small, hence removal efficiency decreases. Maximum removal efficiency at 100 μm particle size of *Citrus limetta* and *Citrus lemon* were found to be 61.3% and 30.1% respectively.

Effect of contact time on removal efficiency :

The experiments were carried out, with change in contact time from 20–100 min and maintain others as constant i.e. adsorbent dosage 12 g L⁻¹; particle size of biomass 150 μm; the concentration of metal ion cadmium(II) 200 mg L⁻¹; pH 4. Initially the removal ef-

iciency increases but after 80 min, it becomes constant as shown in Fig. 6. The result shows that when we increase contact time, more time is available for contact of metal with bio-sorbent, so removal efficiency increases. But after 80 min, the contact time does not prove to be effective because effective time is already taken.

Effect of metal ion concentration on removal efficiency :

The experiments were carried out, with change in metal ion concentration from 50–250 mg L⁻¹ and maintaining other conditions as constant i.e. adsorbent dosage 12 g L⁻¹; particle size of biomass 150 μm; the contact time 80 min; pH 4. As we increase the concentration of metal ion, the adsorption % decreases as shown in Fig. 7. This occurs because the numbers of active sites are fixed in the adsorbent, so when we increase the concentration of metal ion, the competition within metal ions increases for occupying on the adsorbent. So, due to unavailability of adsorbent sites, the adsorption decreases.

Fig. 1. Langmuir adsorption isotherm.

Fig. 2. Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

Fig. 3. Effect of biomass dosages on removal of Cd^{II} ions.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on removal of Cd^{II} ions.

Fig. 5. Effect of particle size on removal of Cd^{II} ions.

Conclusion

The present research concludes that activated *Citrus limetta* peel powder is more effective adsorbent in the removal of Cd^{II} than *Citrus lemon*. Experimental data shows that the adsorption efficiency is dependent on bio adsorbent as well as operating variable such as adsorbent dosage, pH, particle size, contact time and metal ion concentration. The adsorption data fit well with Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm model. This process

Fig. 6. Effect of contact time on removal of Cd^{II} ions.

Fig. 7. Effect of metal ion concentration on removal of Cd^{II} ions.

is easy to carry out and economically feasible for effluent treatment. We can also suggest that ion exchange and hydrogen bonding as the principal mechanism for the removal of Cd^{II} ions by activated *Citrus limetta* peel powder.

Material and methods :

Preparation of bio-sorbent :

The peels of *Citrus limetta* and *Citrus lemon* were collected from various juice centers of Jodhpur. They were cleaned and dried in sunlight and put in oven for 40 h at optimum temperature. The peels were then subjected to mechanical grinder and sieved. The peel powder activated and finally the products obtained were stored in glass bottle for further use.

Cd^{II} solution :

A stock solution containing Cd^{II} (1000 ppm) was prepared in double distilled water. The test solutions that were prepared out of stock solutions were further diluted with required amount of distilled water. These solutions contained metal ions with concentration ranging from 50 to 250 ppm.

Adsorption experiment :

Adsorption experiments were carried out by batch experiment as function of metal concentration (50, 100, 150, 200 and 250) mg L⁻¹, pH (2–6), adsorbent dosage (3–15) g, contact time (20, 40, 60, 80 and 100) min and particle size (100–300 μm).

Parameters were changed according at a time and all other parameters were maintained constant according to Table 1. After completion of every set of experiment finally metal bearing solution were allowed to settle and then the residual metal ion solutions were filtered using Whatmann no. 42 filter paper. The 20 mL of each sample was stored for residual Cd^{II} analysis.

the above eq. (2) can be rearranged in following linear form

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{bq_{\max}} + \frac{1}{q_{\max}} C_e \quad (3)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration, q_e is the amount of metal ion adsorbed, q_{max} is q_e for a complete mono layer (mg L⁻¹). A graph of C_e versus C_e/q_e should indicate a straight line of slope 1/q_{max} and an intercept of 1/bq_{max} as shown in Fig. 1.

Freundlich has found that if the concentration of solute in solvent at equilibrium C_e (mg L⁻¹) is raised to the power of m, the amount of solute adsorbed being q_e, then

Table 1. Experimental conditions

Experimental conditions	M _s (g L ⁻¹)	pH	P _s (μm)	T (min)	C _o (mg L ⁻¹)
Effect of adsorbent dosage M _s (g L ⁻¹)	3–15	4	150	80	200
Effect of pH	12	2–6	150	80	200
Effect of particle size P _s (μm)	12	4	100–300	80	200
Effect of contact time T (min)	12	4	150	20–100	200
Effect of concentration of Cu ^{II} ion C _o (mg L ⁻¹)	12	4	150	80	50–250

Table 2. Langmuir and Freundlich model parameters estimated from the fitting of experimental point of cadmium(II) adsorption

	Langmuir isotherm			Freundlich isotherm		
	R ²	I _{max} (mg g ⁻¹)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	R ²	K _f (mg g ⁻¹)	m
<i>Citrus limetta</i>	0.931	16.63	0.101	0.999	7.86	1.347
<i>Citrus lemon</i>	0.987	12.97	0.077	0.999	6.208	1.323

After the completion of experiment, the concentration of residual Cd^{II} ion was directly measured by atomic adsorption spectroscopy.

Eq. (1) is used to determine the percentage adsorption of metal (φ, in %) by adsorbent.

$$\phi = \frac{C_o - C_e}{C_o} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where C_o is initial metal ion concentration and C_e is the concentration of metal ion after adsorption.

Adsorption isotherm :

According to Langmuir theory, the saturated monolayer isotherm can be represented as :

$$q_e = \frac{q_{\max} bC_e}{1 + bC_e} \quad (2)$$

C_e^m/q_e is a constant at a given temperature. This fairly satisfactory empirical isotherm can be used for non ideal sorption and is expressed by the following equation in the form of logarithm of both sides as shown in Fig. 2.

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + m \log C_e \quad (4)$$

An adsorption isotherm is characterized by certain constant, the value of which express the surface properties and affinity of the adsorbent and can also be used to compare bio-sorptive capacity of biomass for different metal ions. Out of several isotherm equations, two have been applied for this study i.e. the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms.

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